

Welcome! In this study, we are trying to understand how survivors of tech-abuse such as spying, stalking, harassment by an intimate partner may reach out to their friends, families, and colleagues for support.

SHOW CONSENT FORM

We will be asking about your experience with technology abuse, such as spying, stalking, tracking, and harassment by an intimate partner using technology. This could be an experience that you had, or you may have helped a friend, family member, or acquaintance. We will also ask about the context in which the tech abuse occurred, what help was given/received, and how effective this help was.

Before starting the focus-group, I want to let you know that there is no right or wrong answer to any of the questions. We are only interested in your experiences and your honest opinion. So feel free to add as many points as you like to the questions in the interview, and please ask me whatever questions you have as we go. Please be advised that we may not be able to advise on your specific situation; we are mainly here to learn from you and your experience.

I understand this may be a very difficult conversation for you to engage in, and I appreciate any information you can provide. **You do not have to answer any questions that make you feel uncomfortable, and if at any time you would like to stop participating for any reason, you can do so without any penalty.** We appreciate your participation.

- Discuss the consent form with the client, if given consent start recording.
- Make sure I notice the term used for the abusive partner and use it consistently

Experience with the Abuse

Characterizing tech abuse

1. Have you ever felt that a partner was using technology to control, harass, intimidate or stalk you? Can you tell us about those incidents?
[If “helped a survivor”] Can you tell us about the technology abuse the person you helped with was experiencing?
 - a. Which type/form(s) of technology did the partner use to abuse?
 - b. Is this happening now, or did it happen in the past?
 - c. How did you learn about the tech abuse? What initially made you suspicious about the tech-abuse?
 - d. Was the partner living with you in the same household at the time of tech-abuse?
 - e. What is the status of the relationship now?

Taking Action on tech Abuse

Finding help

Did you ask anyone for help? Who did you ask for help?

If yes, ask the following question

1. [Reason to discuss] What is your relationship with them? How long have you known that person?
 - a. How did you decide that you should talk to that person?
 - b. How is this decision based on their technical knowledge, closeness to the survivor, proximity, etc.?
 - c. **Apprehensions?**
2. [What discussed] What help did you ask from that person? How did that person help you in coping with the tech abuse?
 - a. Did the information they provided help you in any way? How?
 - i. Did you feel better after their help?
 - b. Was the help you received sufficient to redress the tech abuse? Why or why not?
3. [Formal help] Did they refer you to seek formal help? How did you reach out to those formal services? [if sought formal help]
 - a. Did someone accompany you when you sought help?
 - b. Did it solve the problem without <support – fill this with whomever they sought support from>?

- c. [if not]
- 4. [Details of communication] Some other details of the communication:
 - a. How did you communicate with the person? (Online or in-person)
 - b. How soon after you discovered the incident did you decide to talk to the support?

If no, ask the following questions

- 1. [Apprehensions] Why did you decide not to discuss this with anyone?
 - a. Were there any other people or groups you wanted to contact, but were not able to do so? Why not?
- 2. Did you use any online resources to mitigate the tech-abuse? Did you find what you were looking for?
 - a. What types of information were you looking for?
 - b. Did you find anything helpful?
 - c. Did the information you found lead you to take any action? What were those actions?

Social Context and Network

Survivor Context

- 1. When you are feeling stressed or upset,
 - a. Are there people in your life can you reach out to for help and support?
 - b. ~~b.~~—Is the abusive partner close to your social circle? Mutual friends?
- 2. Did the abuser in any way try to control who you talk to or meet?
OR How have your relationships in your social circle been impacted by this abusive relationship/incident?

Non-Tech abuse

Characterizing non-tech abuse

- 1. Have you ever experienced any other forms of abuse such as physical, psychological, emotional, sexual, or financial? [verbal]
- 2. For other kinds of abuse, who, if anyone, did you reach out for support?
 - a. Was it helpful in redressing the abuse?
 - b. Were you looking for different kinds of support for this abuse vs. tech-abuse?
 - c. Was this the help you were looking for?

3. Did you talk about both the abuse patterns at the same time?

Perceptions & Recommendations

1. Was the other abuse <replace with the survivor's situation> closely connected/related with technology abuse?

Perception of tech-abuse

1. Before you experienced this tech abusive behavior,
 - a. What do you think about the current forms of support being available?
2. After experiencing this abusive behavior,
 - a. Has your opinion of tech abuse changed at all? How?
 - b. Has your opinion of **your** support-seeking behavior changed at all? How?
3. Do you think any other forms of support *could [have]* helped you?

Demographics

1. [Send google form to the participant - https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1UL5lg2_bgIAN9yYyXHxHqBs4h8PrNR6EpaM9lij55Cc/e/dit#responses]
2. Participant's gender, ethnicity, age, highest level of education, employment status, income, native language

Technical Background & Context

2. How comfortable are you with technology? Do you have a technical background?

Abuser Technical Background & Context

1. Does the partner have a background in technology? What is it?

[If not ongoing] Is the partner living with you now?

3. Partner's background?

Given Help [for survivors who have helped someone else]

1. You have mentioned in the recruitment form that you have also helped someone else with tech abuse.
 - a. Can you describe what they were experiencing especially related to tech-abuse?

- b. How did you know that person?
- c. What kind of help did you provide? What did they ask from you?
- d. What made you help them?
- e. Did you experience tech abuse prior to them asking you for support?
- f. [if yes] Was your own experience with tech-abuse useful in helping them?

Advice

1. Looking back on this tech abuse experience, is there any advice you would give people who are in similar situations? What worked or didn't work for you?
2. In your opinion, what should
 - a. friends, family, roommates or partners, and (or other similar groups) do to prevent this tech abuse, or to help survivors?
3. Do you have any questions for me? Do you have any comments on the interview procedure?